

QUIZ**LAST NAME: ADULOJU****FIRST NAME: GBEMISOLA****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Based on Write Source 2000, building good writing habits may follow which of these four forms:**

- Building, Reviewing, Writing and Thinking.¹**
- Copying, Editing, Developing and Drawing.
- Reviewing, Processing, Developing and Copying.
- Editing, Copying, Revising and Searching.

2. **Each paragraph in the body of the essay should contain which of the following listed below.**

- A topic sentence, supporting sentences, evidence and analysis.²**

¹ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 3.

² Abel Scribe. *CMS Crib Sheet* (2006), 3.

- Opening sentence, evidence, analysis and concluding statement.
- Opening sentence, analysis and concluding statement.
- Opening statement only.

3. **Capitalization may follow which of these three forms:**

- Abbreviations, footnotes and inquiry.
- Full caps and heading caps.
- Full caps, heading caps or sentence caps.**³
- End of quotation.

4. **Good writers will use italics to do which of the following:**

- State a point.
- Emphasize a key word or phrase and foreign terms.
- Emphasize a key word or phrase, titles and foreign terms.**⁴
- To state an argument.

5. **All quotations must include the following:**

- In text citations only.

³ Abel Scribe, 2.

⁴ Ibid, 4.

- A citation, a note or parenthetical citation referring the reader to the source document. Place the citation after the terminal quotation.⁵**
- A parenthetical citation followed by endnotes.
- A note bibliography only.
6. **Ellipsis points are normally not used in which of the following situations:**
- When the original punctuation is deleted.
- When the original punctuation is retained.
- Before the first word of a quotation, even if the beginning of the original sentence has been omitted; or after the last word of a quotation, even if the end of the original sentence has been omitted.⁶**
- When the original punctuation is required.
7. **A comma should be utilized in which of the following scenarios:**
- Set off the elements of a series of two things.’
- Separate two interchangeable clauses.
- Set off introductory elements and items in a series.⁷**
- Separate two words.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian. *Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*, Eight Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 208.

⁶ Abel Scribe, 6.

⁷ The European Commission. 2011. ‘English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission.’ Accessed 15 March 2020. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/mitMjHAGfJ/16>.

8. **According to Turabian, what is required of an Author when they are citing articles and other pieces from newspapers?**

- The Author must cite articles and other pieces from newspapers only in notes.⁸**
- Cite introduction and supporting paragraphs.
- Cite comprehensive and informative analysis of the main topic.
- Cite story and literary information of the topic.

9. **An example of a cliché is best represented by the following statement:**

- It is never over.
- We went on a whirlwind tour.⁹**
- It is just what we said it would be.
- It is not over yet.

10. **An example of a superlative is which of the following below:**

- Congruent.
- Seamless.
- Unprecedented.¹⁰**
- Consistent.

n.d.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 113.

⁹ John Allen, *The BBC News Style Guide* (<http://bbctraining.com>, 2003), 25.

¹⁰ John Allen, 65.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper and Verne Meyer. 2000. *A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning: Write Source*. Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999.

Scribe, Abel, *CMS Crib Sheet*, 2006. <http://www.docstyles.com>. (accessed March 15, 2020).

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

The European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 2011. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/xitMjHAGfJ/> (accessed March 15, 2020.)

John Allen, *The BBC News Style Guide*, 2003. <http://bbctraining.com>. (accessed March 15, 2020).

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.